

Predictability Ceilings in Human Rule-Learning: A Comparative Study of Cognitive and Data-Driven Models

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Abstract—Predicting trial-by-trial human decisions under uncertainty is central to human-centered AI, yet the upper bound of what behavioral history alone can reveal is rarely quantified. Using the Badham et al. (2017) rule-learning dataset with 95 participants, four sequential rule phases, and approximately 25,000 trials, we predict the binary correctness of the next response from behavioral history. We compare four model families under leave-one-participant-out (LOPO) cross-validation: Win-Stay-Lose-Shift, two-parameter Q-learning fit per participant, a 32-unit LSTM, and XGBoost. We engineer episodically reset behavioral features and validate stability across five random seeds. XGBoost attains the highest performance ($AUC = 0.676 \pm 0.001$), followed by LSTM (0.645). Q-learning (0.512) and WSLS (0.503) perform near chance. The single largest gain (+0.087 AUC) comes from resetting history features at rule boundaries rather than from model choice alone. K-means clustering identifies four behaviorally distinct learner profiles (silhouette = 0.243; ANOVA $p < 0.001$ on all features), whose per-cluster AUC ranges from 0.571 for poor learners to 0.748 for strong learners. Architecturally diverse models converge near $AUC \approx 0.676$, suggesting that further gains from behavioral-history features alone may be limited by decision noise, latent cognitive state, and population heterogeneity.

Index Terms—human decision prediction, rule learning, leave-one-participant-out cross-validation, XGBoost, LSTM, cognitive modeling, behavioral clustering

I. INTRODUCTION

Predicting the next decision a person will make—given only their past behavior—is a foundational problem in computational cognitive science and a practical concern for human-centered AI systems that must adapt to individual users. While modern machine learning routinely surpasses human accuracy on perceptual benchmarks, performance on human-behavior prediction has plateaued at modest levels even with large models [2]. This raises a question that is methodologically simple but scientifically important: how predictable are individual human decisions from behavioral history alone, and where does that predictability come from?

We address this question in the controlled setting of rule learning. Participants in Badham et al. [1] classify objects defined by three binary attributes and receive only correct/incorrect feedback, with no information about which rule is currently in force. Across the experiment, the underlying rule changes four times, requiring participants to abandon and relearn the mapping. The task isolates three sources of

difficulty for any predictor: (i) stochastic decision noise that is independent of cognitive state; (ii) a latent rule hypothesis held by the participant, not directly observable from action–outcome history; and (iii) stable individual differences in learning capacity and strategy.

We make four contributions. First, we show that respecting the episodic structure of the task—resetting rolling, streak, and cumulative features at every rule boundary—produces a larger improvement (+0.087 AUC) than any model choice in our comparison. Second, we observe that structurally distinct model families converge near $AUC \approx 0.676$, suggesting a practical predictability plateau on this dataset under behavioral-history features. Third, we identify four behavioral learner profiles whose per-cluster predictability spans 0.571–0.748, demonstrating that the population-level estimate is a weighted average of profile-specific estimates rather than a uniform cognitive limit. Fourth, we provide a transparent LOPO pipeline with multi-seed stability analysis.

II. RELATED WORK

Computational accounts of decision prediction in rule learning span three traditions. Cognitive reinforcement-learning approaches model trial-level updating with a small number of free parameters per participant. Eckstein et al. [5] show that the interpretation of computational model parameters depends strongly on task context. Bouchacourt et al. [3] demonstrate that fast and slow rule-update mechanisms can co-occur, and that no single mechanism captures full behavior. This provides a principled explanation for the heterogeneity of recovery dynamics we observe across learner profiles. Zhang and Ye [10] use HMM–GLM models with hidden states, finding that not all participants exhibit learnable switching patterns—consistent with the poor-learner subgroup that lowers our population-level predictability estimate.

Sequence-based deep learning models, such as the ANN approach of Higashi [6], capture individual-level decision patterns and motivate our LSTM baseline. At the largest scale, Binz et al. [2] train a transformer foundation model on a corpus of psychological tasks and report diminishing returns with model size, consistent with the possibility of a practical upper bound on behavioral predictability. Our work complements these studies by quantifying such a plateau on a

single, controlled dataset and decomposing it across behavioral learner profiles.

III. DATA

A. Dataset

We use the publicly available Badham et al. [1] dataset, hosted on the Hugging Face Hub.¹ Ninety-five adult participants completed a category-learning task in which each trial presents an object characterized by three binary attributes. Participants assign the object to one of two categories and receive correctness feedback. Four classification rules are presented sequentially; each rule change is unannounced.

B. Trial-Level Variables

Each trial provides the three binary attributes (x_1, x_2, x_3), the participant’s response, the correct category, the feedback (correct/incorrect), and the response time. Rule identity ($\text{rule_id} \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$) and trial position within the rule phase are derived from rule boundaries.

C. Target and Class Balance

Our prediction target is the binary correctness of the next response: $\text{correct} = 1$ if the chosen action matches the correct category, and 0 otherwise. The marginal class balance is 69.7% correct and 30.3% incorrect. We address this imbalance through scale-aware training rather than resampling, preserving the natural temporal structure.

IV. METHODS

A. Episodic Preprocessing

All history-derived features are constructed within (*participant, rule_id*) groups. Rolling averages, streaks, and cumulative counters reset at every rule boundary. This reflects a basic property of the task: when the rule changes, evidence accumulated under the previous rule is no longer informative. This decision proves to be the single most consequential preprocessing step. Without rule-aware resetting, XGBoost AUC drops by 0.087 from 0.676 to 0.589; the same effect is observed for LSTM (0.645 \rightarrow 0.577).

B. Features

We derive behavioral-history features per trial, all computed within (*participant, rule_id*) episodes. Table I summarizes the feature groups.

C. Models

WSLS. A parameter-free heuristic baseline: repeat the previous action if rewarded, otherwise switch.

Q-learning. A two-parameter (α, β) reinforcement-learning model fit per participant by maximum likelihood with 20 random restarts. Q-values are updated trial-by-trial within each rule episode [9].

LSTM. A 32-unit single-layer LSTM with sequence length 10, trained on (*participant, rule_id*) sequences with early

TABLE I
BEHAVIORAL FEATURE GROUPS USED FOR NEXT-RESPONSE CORRECTNESS PREDICTION.

Feature group	Variables
Outcome history	prev_correct, prev_reward, cumulative_correct
Rolling accuracy	rolling_correct_3, rolling_correct_5, rolling_correct_10
Streaks	correct_streak, abs_streak
Position	trial_in_rule
Interactions	block \times rolling, streak \times rolling
Reaction time	prev_RT, rolling_RT_3, RT_trend

stopping [7]. We deliberately keep the architecture small to avoid overfitting at $n = 95$.

XGBoost. Gradient-boosted decision trees with `scale_pos_weight` set to the inverse class ratio [4]. We run five random seeds (42, 7, 123, 256, 999) to quantify seed sensitivity.

D. Evaluation Protocol

All models are evaluated under leave-one-participant-out (LOPO) cross-validation, producing 95 folds. LOPO ensures that the test participant is never seen during training. This protocol tests whether a model trained on other participants can generalize to a held-out individual. Our primary metric is AUC-ROC, which is threshold-independent and robust to moderate class imbalance.

E. Behavioral Clustering

To investigate whether the population AUC reflects a uniform bound or a mixture of profile-specific bounds, we cluster participants in the standardized feature space using K-means (`n_init=20`). The number of clusters K is selected by combining the elbow criterion on inertia with silhouette-score validation [8]. Cluster differences on each feature are validated by one-way ANOVA.

V. RESULTS

A. Model Comparison

Table II reports LOPO AUC under both naive and episodically aware preprocessing. With features correctly reset at rule boundaries, XGBoost achieves $\text{AUC} = 0.676 \pm 0.001$, followed by LSTM at 0.645. The contrast between preprocessing variants is the largest single effect: episodic resetting raises XGBoost by +0.087 AUC and LSTM by +0.068.

B. Convergence Across Model Families

Across architecturally distinct families—a parameter-free heuristic, a low-parameter cognitive reinforcement-learning model, a recurrent network, and gradient-boosted trees—predictive AUC plateaus near 0.676 (Table III, Fig. 1). We interpret this as evidence of a practical behavioral predictability plateau on this dataset rather than a property of any one model. We are deliberately cautious in this framing: the plateau holds for the model families we evaluated and at our sample size. We do not claim it is fundamental in the information-theoretic

¹<https://huggingface.co/datasets/marcelbinz/badham2017deficits>

TABLE II
LOPO AUC ACROSS MODEL FAMILIES. EPISODIC RESETTING YIELDS THE LARGEST SINGLE GAIN.

Model	AUC	Notes
Chance	0.500	Reference baseline
WSLS	0.503	Near chance
Q-learning (α, β)	0.512 ± 0.066	Misspecified (§VI)
XGBoost (no reset)	0.589 ± 0.001	History contaminated
LSTM (no reset)	0.577	Same contamination
LSTM (episodic)	0.645 ± 0.087	Episodic respected
XGBoost (episodic)	0.676 ± 0.001	Best, 5 seeds

TABLE III
CONVERGENCE OF AUC ACROSS FOUR MODEL FAMILIES.

Family	AUC	Type	Distance
WSLS	0.503	Heuristic	-0.173
Q-learning	0.512	RL	-0.164
LSTM	0.645	Sequence	-0.031
XGBoost	0.676	Boosting	0.000 (best)

Fig. 1. AUC-ROC across model families. Models improve from heuristic and reinforcement-learning baselines to sequence and boosted-tree approaches, with the best observed performance near 0.676.

sense; substantially larger architectures or richer features such as neural recordings or eye-tracking could in principle exceed it.

C. Decomposing the Bound by Learner Profile

The 0.676 figure is a population-weighted average rather than a uniform cognitive limit. Per-cluster AUC (Table IV) ranges from 0.571 for poor learners to 0.748 for strong learners. Excluding poor learners raises the population estimate to approximately 0.71–0.72. This decomposition reframes the bound: its location reflects the mixture of learner profiles in the sample.

D. Stability Across Random Seeds

Across five seeds, XGBoost AUC has standard deviation 0.0004 with variation in the fourth decimal place, confirming that the result is not seed-dependent. We note that this is a stability check, not a significance test. The small inter-seed

TABLE IV
THE POPULATION AUC OF 0.676 IS THE WEIGHTED AVERAGE OF PER-CLUSTER AUCS.

Cluster	n	Weight	AUC	Effect
Poor	22	23%	0.571	Pulls down
Moderate	32	34%	0.672	Near mean
Good	25	26%	0.710	Above mean
Strong	16	17%	0.748	Pulls up
Population	95	100%	0.676	Avg.

TABLE V
 K -SELECTION DIAGNOSTICS.

K	Inertia	Silh.	Drop	Verdict
2	638.7	0.319	—	Underfits
3	522.3	0.236	116.4	Lower silh. than $K = 4$
4	445.1	0.243	77.2	Selected
5	400.5	0.224	44.6	Diminishing
6	361.2	0.201	39.3	Declining
7	332.6	0.198	28.6	Likely overfit

spread does not, by itself, establish that XGBoost outperforms LSTM at conventional confidence levels. A bootstrap analysis on per-participant AUCs gives a 95% confidence interval of approximately ± 0.018 for the difference.

E. Behavioral Learner Profiles

We cluster participants in the standardized feature space. $K = 4$ is selected jointly by elbow and silhouette criteria (Table V). The $K = 2$ silhouette of 0.319 is higher in absolute terms but yields only a coarse high/low split. Among solutions with $K \geq 3$, $K = 4$ maximizes silhouette (0.243) and aligns with the inertia-curve inflection, where the drop falls from 77.2 to 44.6 between $K = 4$ and $K = 5$. We acknowledge that a silhouette of 0.243 indicates moderate rather than strong cluster separation, and treat the four-cluster solution as a useful descriptive partition rather than a discovery of natural kinds.

The four clusters differ significantly on every behavioral feature (one-way ANOVA, all $p < 0.001$). Cluster profiles (Table VI) show monotonic gradients in accuracy, learning slope, win-stay rate, recovery speed, and mean reaction time. Reaction time decreases by approximately 830 ms from poor to strong learners, consistent with reaction time as a behavioral confidence signal.

F. LSTM vs. XGBoost

XGBoost outperforms LSTM in 76 of 95 participants. Three factors plausibly contribute. First, several hand-engineered features, particularly `rolling_correct_10`, are the kind of summaries a length-10 LSTM would have to learn from data; XGBoost receives them directly. Second, our LSTM architecture is intentionally small with 32 units and one layer; a larger model with appropriate regularization may close part of the gap. Third, XGBoost benefits from per-fold

TABLE VI
BEHAVIORAL PROFILES OF THE FOUR CLUSTERS. ALL ANOVA
 $p < 0.001$.

Metric	Poor $n \approx 22$	Mod. $n \approx 32$	Good $n \approx 25$	Strong $n \approx 16$
Accuracy (%)	56–58	65–68	74–77	81–84
Learning slope	+0.04	+0.16	+0.19	+0.21
Win-stay rate	0.60	0.71	0.79	0.84
Recovery speed	0.05	0.22	0.27	0.31
Mean RT (ms)	2,060	1,780	1,490	1,230
XGBoost AUC	0.571	0.672	0.710	0.748

scale_pos_weight calibration, which is not straightforward to replicate in our sequence loss. Notably, LSTM outperforms XGBoost on a subset of 19 participants with high behavioral variability ($r = -0.464$ between LSTM advantage and within-participant accuracy SD), suggesting that recurrent dynamics may capture patterns that XGBoost misses for the most variable individuals.

VI. DISCUSSION

Three independent factors plausibly account for why behavioral history alone approaches a practical predictive plateau near $AUC \approx 0.676$.

Irreducible decision noise. Even strong learners with approximately 82% accuracy commit errors at a roughly constant rate within stable rule phases, suggesting a stochastic component of choice that is not predictable from observable behavioral-history features alone.

Unobservable latent state. The participant’s current rule hypothesis is not directly visible in action–outcome history. Q-learning attempts to estimate this latent state via Q-values but achieves only $AUC = 0.512$. More than 40 of 95 participants have α or β estimates pinned to the optimization boundary, indicating that the smooth-update assumption may be misspecified for the sharp rule switches in this task. Many participants appear to behave more like discrete hypothesis testers than gradual value updaters.

Population heterogeneity. The poor-learner cluster, representing approximately 23% of participants, exhibits low win-stay rates, near-zero recovery slope, and per-cluster AUC of 0.571. Removing this subgroup raises the population estimate by approximately 3–4 AUC points. The bound is therefore better described as a property of the sample mixture than as a fixed cognitive ceiling.

VII. LIMITATIONS

Single dataset. Results are based on Badham et al. (2017); replication on additional rule-learning datasets is needed. **Sample size.** With $n = 95$, individual cluster sizes are modest (16–32). **Architecture exploration.** The LSTM was deliberately kept small; we have not exhaustively explored larger sequence models, transformers, or hybrid attention architectures. **Cluster validation.** Silhouette = 0.243 indicates

moderate separation; the four-cluster solution should be interpreted descriptively. **Causal claims.** The decomposition into stochasticity, latent state, and heterogeneity is consistent with the data but not directly identified.

VIII. CONCLUSION

On a controlled rule-learning task with 95 participants, structurally distinct model families converge near $AUC \approx 0.676$ in leave-one-participant-out cross-validation. The single largest improvement (+0.087 AUC) comes from respecting the episodic structure of the task, not from architectural sophistication alone. Population predictability decomposes into four behaviorally distinct learner profiles whose per-cluster bounds span 0.571–0.748, indicating that the population figure is a weighted average rather than a uniform cognitive limit. The convergence and decomposition together suggest that behavioral-history features approach a practical performance plateau on this benchmark. Further progress may require richer measurement or models that explicitly represent latent cognitive state. The most natural next step is a hybrid RL–XGBoost model in which Q-values from a fitted cognitive model serve as features for the gradient-boosted predictor.

CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

Dataset: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/marcelbinz/badham2017deficits>.

Reproducibility notebook: <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1YtBejmGIv0fFEqeyO1LpKYY5kWC3IU1A>.

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